

USE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: *Russian language teaching methodology is an interdisciplinary discipline located at the intersection of several sciences (pedagogy, psychology, philosophy, linguistics and social pedagogy), and defining the principles, methods, techniques and content of education.*

Keywords: *Methodology, Russian language, teaching, combination, training, student, skill.*

INTRODUCTION

The subject of the methodology of teaching Russian is quite extensive and includes: the necessary language material, which must be mastered by students in order to obtain language skills; the activities of the teacher, aimed at selecting the necessary educational material and methods of its "submission" to students; the activities of the teacher in organizing the educational process, which includes not only the presentation of the necessary educational material to students, but also the implementation of diagnostic methods aimed at identifying the level of knowledge and skills; activities of students aimed at mastering the necessary knowledge and skills, as well as developing skills within the framework of the studied academic discipline.

MAIN PART

The technique is aimed at solving the following problems:¹

1. Why it is necessary to learn Russian - includes setting goals and objectives for learning.
2. What should be taught - reveals the content of training, the validity of the developed program, the use of specific textbooks and workbooks, manuals.

¹ Malakhovskiy V.A. Methodology of the Russian language. - M., 2015.

3. How to teach - includes the development of teaching methods and techniques, the structure of the lesson and the cycle of the subject, educational equipment and teaching aids.

4. How to monitor the assimilation of educational material - the definition of the main methods of control and evaluation criteria.

The content of teaching the Russian language, in accordance with the teaching methodology, includes:²

1. The choice by the teacher of a specific scientific concept, on which the entire educational process organized by him will be based in the future.

2. Selection of sufficient and necessary terminological and conceptual apparatus.

3. A clear definition of the range of knowledge, skills and abilities that each student should master as a result of studying the academic discipline.

Teaching Russian language is a joint activity of a teacher and students. In order for students to master the language, the teacher must carry out certain educational (teaching) actions: explain new material, give a task, ask a question and check the correctness of the answer, etc. Students should also be active and carry out a number of actions during the educational process: read the text, learn the words, do the exercises, answer the teacher's questions, etc.

Teaching the Russian language, even in the absence of a language environment, is understood as teaching speech, communication and expression of thought in Russian. Thus, the methodology has its own subject of study, which is not repeated in any of the sciences - teaching another language as a means of communication. This category determines the content of the entire educational process, the types of speech activities that need to be learned, the levels of language proficiency that must be achieved in each of these types.

Methodology and its basic sciences

The basic science for the methodology is linguistics (linguistics). Teaching practice shows that not every way of describing the Russian language is equally effective when it comes to teaching students (foreigners). Without the participation of linguistics, it is also impossible to make teaching effective.

Didactic principles in language teaching

Didactics is a department of pedagogy that outlines general teaching methods.

² Ramzaeva T.G., Lvov M.R. Methods of teaching the Russian language in elementary grades. - M.: Education, 2019.

Psychology is the main basic science of methodology

Most of the laws governing the educational process are of a psychological nature, which is why psychology is considered the main basic science for methodology.

Psychological theory of speech activity

Communication is an activity. Activity can be not only communicative: there is labor activity, cognitive (educational), gaming. But it always has a fundamentally unified psychological structure, which means that the patterns of its formation are also the same. It follows from this that both communication and teaching such communication must obey general psychological laws.

What does it mean to "teach activities"

Any training is training of this or that activity. So, teaching Russian as a foreign language is teaching speech activity using this language. If we teach speech activity, then our main task is to build the necessary speech operations and "add" the necessary speech actions from them.

The most important criteria are distinguished by which the formation of skills is judged: unconsciousness, complete automaticity, compliance with the norm of the language being studied, normal pace of execution, stability.

But in order to speak, one must be able to combine individual skills with each other into a system. Possessing speech skills does not mean that the student already knows how to communicate in the language. There are two more things to learn:

- use speech skills in order to independently express their thoughts, feelings, experiences;
- clearly vary the choice and combination of speech operations depending on the purpose, situation. When a person knows how to do all this, it means that he has formed communicative and speech skills.

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